

USE OF LATIN TERMINOLOGY IN THE PROFESSIONAL ACTIVITY OF A
DOCTOR (BASED ON THE MATERIAL OF AN OUTPATIENT'S MEDICAL CARD)

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Abstract. This article discusses ways of explicating special medical concepts in the texts of medical records of outpatients. A correlation is made between the way a term is written and its belonging to the anatomical-histological nomenclature and the system of clinical terminology.

Key words: medical terminology, outpatient medical record, medical discourse, natural written speech.

Currently, researchers identify a paradigm of medical communication, which is ordinary professional medical discourse, ordinary non-professional medical discourse, professional medical discourse, pseudo-medical discourse [4, p. 131]. Currently, texts that can be attributed to different components of this paradigm are being actively studied (in this case, we used the concept of “text” in its broadest sense: “text is the basic unit of communication” [6, p. 193]). They are analyzed from the perspective of a variety of research strategies, since they vary significantly in genre, functional, pragmatic, discursive, narratological, and stylistic terms. In particular, the everyday understanding of medical terms [4, 13], definitional modeling [8, 12], various aspects of medical discourse [1, 5], and medical metaphor [9] are described. We took as an object of study a text intended for professional communication, that is, a text included in professional medical discourse—the medical record of an outpatient.

We analyzed this genre formation from the standpoint of the Barnaul-Kemerovo school of natural written speech, based on the developed system for describing objects of natural written speech [7]. As a result of the study, genre-relevant and genre-irrelevant, but frequent, features of the natural written speech of a doctor filling out an outpatient medical record were identified, which allowed us to conclude that these texts are on the periphery of the genres of natural written speech [3]. Although the entries in the medical record are on the periphery of professional medical texts, such as an article, monograph, etc. (on the periphery from the point of view of his preparedness), they represent part of professional medical discourse. This material allows us to trace exactly how medical terminology is presented in the natural (spontaneous) written speech of a practicing doctor.

According to reviews from doctors, very often the text of a medical record is not orthologically correct. “An analysis of a large number of outpatient medical records showed that to date the problem of proper management has not been solved” [11, p. 123]. Sometimes this is due to the combination of the patient’s oral, spoken discourse with the written medical discourse of the doctor filling out the chart [see 3].

The purpose of this work is to describe ways of explicating medical terminology of Greek-Latin origin in the medical record of an outpatient. As researchers note, “terminological space is a necessary condition for the formation, development and improvement of a medical specialist” [8, p. 94]. Due to the fact that medical terminology is based on Latin and Greek, and for many centuries Latin was the official language of medicine, medical students not only memorize terms during their training, but also learn anatomical, clinical and pharmaceutical terminology. We tried to identify the extent to which the acquired knowledge is then used professionally in spontaneously produced speech, which is an indirect confirmation of the internalization of the term.

When producing the text of a medical record, the doctor is in a situation of linguistic choice, determined by several aspects. One of them is the synonymy of terms. “Modern medical terminology is one of the most extensive and conceptually and substantively complex systems of terms” [10]. The phenomenon of synonymy is one of the characteristic features of medical terminology itself. Researchers have different views on this problem; types of synonyms have been identified [2]. G. N. Aksenova concludes that in medical terminology, “partial synonyms mainly function” [2]. In this work, we will not dwell on this issue, since it is not within the scope of our research; we will only stipulate that we did not distinguish between partial and complete synonymy. The doctor, recording complaints, symptoms and making a diagnosis, chooses between the Latin and Cyrillic written systems (for example, dacryocystitis and dacryocystitis), between terms of Latin and Russian origin (runny nose and rhinitis), transliterated terms, in addition, he can choose from a group of synonymous designations choose an eponym for the same disease or anatomical formation.

As the analysis of the material shows, in the process of recording patient complaints, doctors most often use standard formulations that have Latin (“vesicular breathing”) or Russian origin “headaches.” At the same time, as a rule, even when writing down terms of Greek-Latin origin, doctors give preference to the Cyrillic system. Terms written in Latin letters make up about 5% of the analyzed records. It should be noted that switching from one system to another occurs immediately, as for example in the following diagnosis: “Flat feet of both feet I-II degree Halluxvalgus” (approx. spelling and punctuation preserved - S.G.). In some entries there is a

tendency to record common words, as seen in the following examples: “slurred speech” and “dysarthria”, “tremor of limbs” and “tremor of limbs”. Moreover, when describing the course of the disease, the doctor can directly record the vocabulary of the patient (or his representative, if we are talking about the pediatrician’s notes): “I got sick yesterday, runny nose, coughing...”. Sometimes the writer uses quotation marks: the patient’s speech is recorded as such, “someone else’s word”: “Complaints about ‘wheezing’.” Accordingly, in texts of this type it is possible to record the intersection of non-professional and professional medical discourses.

Greco-Latin terms written in Latin usually refer to anatomical and histological nomenclature, for example, "Coretpulm b/o". In this case, it would be more correct to even talk not about a term, but about a truncated term element, since the word “pulm” is written without the ending required by the rules of Latin grammar. Abbreviations adopted in anatomical atlases (such as A. basilaris) or general medical terms are also used: St. localis.

Words related to clinical terminology are transliterated and written in Cyrillic in 99% of cases, for example, “periartthritis” or “Ds: congenital internal hydrocephalus” (emphasis added).

Thus, the following conclusions can be drawn. Firstly, in the written speech of doctors, Greek-Latin, Russian terminology and neutral vocabulary are actively used. Latin terms related to clinical terminology are usually transliterated and written in Cyrillic. The Latin alphabet is used for the most part to write terms that, firstly, cannot be transliterated, and secondly, relate to anatomical and histological terminology.

Literature:

1. Karimovna, Y. S., & Farxodovna, R. K. THE EFFECT OF SLEEP ON STUDENT PERFORMANCE. *Zbiór artykułów naukowych recenzowanych.*, 26.
2. Shamsievna, N. Z., & Karimovna, Y. S. LEARNING FOREIGN LANGUAGES FOR MEDICAL INSTITUTIONS. *ЕВРАЗИЙСКИЙ СОЮЗ УЧЕНЫХ (ЕСУ)*, 32.
3. Karimovna, Y. S., Kenjabaevna, A. P., Bakhodirovna, E. M., & Mallaevna, N. S. (2023). PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS IN THE MEDICAL FIELD OF ENGLISH AND UZBEK CULTURES. *DEVELOPMENT AND INNOVATIONS IN SCIENCE*, 2 (2), 10–13.
4. Karimovna, Y. S. (2020). English and Uzbek medical conversation between doctor and patient (Analysis from a linguistic point of view). *Journal of Critical Reviews*, 7(5), 292-294.
5. Ерова, С. (2023). Коммуникатив хатти-ҳаракатлар прагмалингвистика, маданиятлараро прагматика. *Общество и инновации*, 4(7/S), 276-282.
6. Ёрова, С. (2023). ТИББИЙ НУТҚНИНГ ИЖТИМОЙ-МАДАНИЙ АСОСЛАРИ. *Общественные науки в современном мире: теоретические и практические исследования*, 2(1), 35-38.
7. Ёрова, С. К. (2022). Бевосита тиббиётнинг касб компетенцияси ва унинг деонтологик асослари. *Science and Education*, 3(12), 212-218.

8. Ёрова, С. К. (2023). ТИББИЙ НУТҚНИНГ КОГНИТИВ, МАДАНИЙ ВА ПРАГМАТИК ХУСУСИЯТЛАРИ. *IJTIMOIIY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIIY JURNALI*, 3(2), 219-223.
9. Yorova, S. K., & Khakberdiyeva, V. J. K. (2021). DOCTOR AND PATIENT. *Scientific progress*, 2(1), 1478-1480.
10. Yorova, S. (2023). TO STUDY MEDICAL TERMS IN LATIN AND GREEK LANGUAGES. *International Bulletin of Engineering and Technology*, 3(3), 166-170.
11. Mardanovich, M. Z., Aliaskarovna, S. U., Kenjaevna, B. M., Genjebaevna, A. P., & Salimovich, S. B. (2021). Some Considerations about Legal Solutions and Practices of Certain Problems Writing Recipes. *Annals of the Romanian Society for Cell Biology*, 5341-5352.
12. Mukhamadiyeva, M., & Sharipov, B. (2022). LATIN AS THE MAIN LANGUAGE OF MEDICINE. *Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences*, 1(7), 337-339.
13. ZAFAR, M., BOBUR, S., & DILMUROD, B. R. (2021). Scientific and pedagogical basis of teaching the theory of decisions in school chemistry. *International Journal of Philosophical Studies and Social Sciences*, 1(3), 192-196.
14. Mardanovich, M. Z., Salimovich, S. B., & Arzimurodovich, B. D. (2021). Developing Students Attitudes Towards the Environment When Teaching a Foreign Languages. *Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, 1(1), 199-201.
15. Salimovich, S. B. (2022). Studies of Reciprocity in Linguistics. *Eurasian Scientific Herald*, 8, 221-224.
16. Шарипов, Б. С. (2022). ТИЛ БИРЛИКЛАРИНИНГ НУТҚДА FAOLLASHUVI HAQIDA. *МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА*, 5(1).
17. Sharipov, B., Makhmudov, Z., & Buriyev, D. (2023). The role of teaching latin in the course of subject training of future foreign language teachers. *Science and innovation in the education system*, 2(1), 11-14.
18. Makhmudov, Z. M., & Sharipov, B. S. LOTIN TILI VA TIBBIY TERMINOLOGIYA FANINI O'QITISHDA INNOVATSION TEXNOLOGIYALARDAN FOYDALANISHNING DIDAKTIK TAMOYILLARI VA UNING ASOSI HAQIDA FIKRLAR.
19. Sharipov, B., Makhmudov, Z., & Buriyev, D. (2023). Influence of the latin language on the formation of medical terminology. *Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences*, 2(1), 16-20.
20. Sharipov, B., Makhmudov, Z., & Buriyev, D. (2023). Features of teaching latin to students medical universities studying in english. *Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences*, 2(1), 21-25.
21. Makhmudov, Z., Sharipov, B., & Bo'riyev, D. (2023). Tibbiyot universitetlarida lotin tili va tibbiy terminologiya fanini o'qitishning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari. *Science and innovation in the education system*, 2(1), 5-10.
22. Mardanovich, M. Z., Salimovich, S. B., & Arzimurodovich, B. D. (2021). Modern Methods of Teaching Latin and Medical Terminology in Uzbekistan. *International Journal of Development and Public Policy*, 1(5), 190-192.
23. Mardanovich, M. Z., Salimovich, S. B., & Arzimurodovich, B. D. (2021). Reviews of effective use of educational methods in teaching latin and medical

terminology. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(4), 381-386.

24. Sharipov, B. (2023). SOME CONSIDERATIONS ON THE FORMATION OF CLINICAL TERMS IN LATIN. *International Bulletin of Applied Science and Technology*, 3(6), 477-479.

25. Salimovich, S. B. (2022). RECIPROCAL SYMMETRY AND ITS GRAMMATICAL INDICATIONS. *EPRA International Journal of Research and Development (IJRD)*, 7(12), 129-131.

26. Sharipov, B. (2022). RETSIPROKLIK XUSUSIDA MULOHAZALAR. *Общественные науки в современном мире: теоретические и практические исследования*, 1(19), 63-66.

27. Salimovich, S. B. (2022, January). FUNCTIONS OF LANGUAGE UNITS. In *Conference Zone* (pp. 62-63).

28. Mardanovich, M. Z., & Salimovich, S. B. Auditoriyadan tashqari ta'lim-tarbiyaga maqsadli, tizimli yondashish. In *Конференция состоялась 5 марта 2022 года на базе Ташкентского государственного стоматологического института по адресу: Республика Узбекистан, 100047, г. Ташкент, ул. Махтумкули, 103. Цель конференции—знакомство и обмен опытом в обучении и в работе с цифровыми данными, технологиями их применения в гуманитарных* (p. 455).

29. Nasimjanovna, K. F., & Salimovich, S. B. (2023). NAMES OF DISEASES AND THEIR USE IN CLINICAL TERMINOLOGY. *Journal of Universal Science Research*, 1(6), 469-474.

30. Isroilova, M., & Sharipov, B. (2023). SOME OBSERVATIONS ON LATIN PRONUNCIATION AND SPELLING. *Science and innovation in the education system*, 2(7), 127-129.

31. Sharipov, B. (2023). SOME CONSIDERATIONS ON THE FORMATION OF CLINICAL TERMS IN LATIN. *International Bulletin of Applied Science and Technology*, 3(6), 477-479.

32. Salimovich, S. B. (2023). TRANSLATION OF CLINICAL TERMS IN LATIN AND BASIC MEDICAL TERMINOLOGY CLASSES. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 3(3), 100-103.

33. Махмудов, З. М., & Шарипов, Б. С. Талабаларнинг фанни яхши ўрганишлари учун психо-эмоционал таъсир этишда халқ мақол ва маталларидан тўғри фойдаланиш (лотин тили ва тиббий терминология фани мисолида). *Zbiór artykułów naukowych recenzowanych*, 112.

34. Bektoshevna, E. D., & Salimovich, S. B. (2023). LATIN AND GREEK TERMINOLOGY IN THE PROCESS OF STUDY OF OPERATIVE SURGERY. *Yangi O'zbekistonda Tabiiy va Ijtimoiy-gumanitar fanlar respublika ilmiy amaliy konferensiyasi*, 1(6), 66-72.

35. Sharipov Bobur Salimovich. (2023). ESSENTIAL COMMENTS ON THE CHARACTERISTICS DUE TO THE ORIGIN OF CLINICAL TERMS AND FEATURES OF CLINICAL TERMINOLOGY. *Research Focus International Scientific Journal*, 2(6), 144-148. Retrieved from <https://refocus.uz/index.php/1/article/view/296>

36. Salimovich, S. B. (2023). SOME THOUGHTS ON THE IMPORTANCE AND HISTORY OF THE LATIN LANGUAGE IN WORLD LANGUAGES. *Research Focus*, 2(10), 49-53.
37. Mardanovich, M. Z., & Salimovich, S. B. Auditoriyadan tashqari ta'lim-tarbiyaga maqsadli, tizimli yondashish. In *Конференция состоялась 5 марта 2022 года на базе Ташкентского государственного стоматологического института по адресу: Республика Узбекистан, 100047, г. Ташкент, ул. Махтумкули, 103. Цель конференции—знакомство и обмен опытом в обучении и в работе с цифровыми данными, технологиями их применения в гуманитарных* (p. 455).
38. Ithomovna, I. S., & Zikirayayevna, S. A. (2023). LEARNING ENGLISH LANGUAGE AS A SECOND LANGUAGE. *Yangi O'zbekistonda Tabiiy va Ijtimoiy-gumanitar fanlar respublika ilmiy amaliy konferensiyasi*, 1(7), 37-43.
39. Zikiryaevna, S. A. (2022). Cognitive Interpretation Of The Phenomenon Of Metonymy. *Eurasian Medical Research Periodical*, 5, 102-104.
40. Zikiryaevna, S. A. (2023). THE ENCOUNTER OF MODERNISM IN ENGLISH LITERATURE. *Ethiopian International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 10(12), 6-8.
41. METONYMY, O. a teacher of department of languages, Medicine and Education faculty Samarkand State Medical Institute. *SCIENTIFIC REPORTS OF BUKHARA STATE UNIVERSITY*, 136(17), 49-52.
42. Шодидулова, А. З. (2023). ГИПОНИМЛАР ҚЎЛЛАНИШИДА КОГЕЗИЯНИНГ НАМОЁН БЎЛИШИ. " XXI ASRDA INNOVATION TEXNOLOGIYALAR, FAN VA TA'LIM TARAQQIYOTIDAGI DOLZARB MUAMMOLAR" nomli respublika ilmiy-amaliy konferensiyasi, 1(11), 111-117.